

Orca: FSS-based Secure Training and Inference with GPUs

(Supplementary Material)

1. Interconversion between Fixed and Float

1.1. Security proof and costs of $\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{FixToFloat}}$

We summarize the costs for $\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{FixToFloat}}$ in Theorem 1 and provide its simulator-based security proof.

Theorem 1. $\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{FixToFloat}}$ realizes $\text{FixToFloat}_{n,f}$ securely such that $\text{keysize}(\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{FixToFloat}}) = \text{keysize}(\Pi_{n,2n,p^{(n)},q^{(n)}}^{\text{MIC}}) + \text{keysize}(\Pi_n^{\text{select}}) + 3n + 1$. In the online phase, the protocol requires 1 evaluation of $\Pi_{n,2n,p^{(n)},q^{(n)}}^{\text{MIC}}$ and communicates $4n + 2$ bits in 2 rounds.

Security Proof. For $b \in \{0, 1\}$, the simulator $\text{Sim}_b^{\text{FixToFloat}}$ for FixToFloat is given \hat{x} and (z_b, s_b, e_b, m_b) and has to simulate the view of party b , i.e., messages $k_b^{(\text{MIC})} || k_b^{(\text{select})} || r_b^{(s)} || r_b^{(u)} || r_b^{(y)} || c_b$ from dealer and $\hat{s}_{1-b} || \hat{u}_{1-b} || \hat{y}_{1-b}$ from the other evaluator. The simulator follows the following steps:

- 1) Randomly samples $r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(s)}$ and $\hat{s}_{1-b,\text{sim}}$ from \mathbb{U}_2 .
- 2) Randomly samples $r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(y)}$, $\hat{y}_{1-b,\text{sim}}$ and $\hat{u}_{1-b,\text{sim}}$ from \mathbb{U}_N .
- 3) Sets $\hat{s}_{\text{sim}} = s_b + r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(s)} + \hat{s}_{1-b,\text{sim}}$.
- 4) Randomly samples $\hat{y}_{b,\text{sim}}$ constrained to the condition that LSB of $\hat{y}_{b,\text{sim}} + b \cdot \hat{x}$ is 0.
- 5) Invokes $\text{Sim}_b^{\text{select}}$ with input $(1 - \hat{s}_{\text{sim}}, \hat{x})$ and output $(\hat{y}_{b,\text{sim}} + b \cdot \hat{x}) \ggg_L 1$ to generate $k_{b,\text{sim}}^{\text{select}}$.
- 6) Sets $\hat{y}_{\text{sim}} = \hat{y}_{b,\text{sim}} + \hat{y}_{1-b,\text{sim}}$
- 7) Randomly samples \hat{u}_{sim} from \mathbb{U}_N and frac from $\mathbb{U}_{2^{2n-24}}$.
- 8) Sets $c_{b,\text{sim}} = m_b \cdot 2^{n-24} + \text{frac} - b \cdot \hat{y}_{\text{sim}} \cdot \hat{u}_{\text{sim}} + r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(y)} \cdot \hat{u}_{\text{sim}} + r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(u)} \cdot \hat{y}_{\text{sim}}$.
- 9) Sets $\hat{u}_{b,\text{sim}} = \hat{u}_{\text{sim}} - \hat{u}_{1-b,\text{sim}}$.
- 10) Randomly samples $\hat{t}_{b,\text{sim}}$ from \mathbb{U}_N^{2n} subject to constraints in line 4,5 and 7 in $\text{Eval}_{n,f}^{\text{FixToFloat}}$.
- 11) Calculates $r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(u)}$ according to line 8 in $\text{Eval}_{n,f}^{\text{FixToFloat}}$.
- 12) Invokes $\text{Sim}_b^{\text{MIC}}$ with input \hat{x} and output $\hat{t}_{b,\text{sim}}$ to generate $k_{b,\text{sim}}^{\text{MIC}}$.

1.2. Protocol for FloatToFix

We present the complete protocol $\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{FloatToFix}}$ for $\text{FloatToFix}_{n,f}$ in Figure 1. We summarize the costs of the protocol in Theorem 2 and provide its security proof.

FloatToFix $\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{FloatToFix}}$

$\text{Gen}_{n,f}^{\text{FloatToFix}}(r^{\text{out}})$:

- 1: $r^{(m)} \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{U}_{2^{24}}$
- 2: $r^{(e')} \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{U}_{1024}$
- 3: $r^{(w)} \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{U}_2$
- 4: $r^{(t)} \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{U}_N$
- 5: $(k_0^<, k_1^<) \leftarrow \text{Gen}_{24}^<(1^\lambda, r^{(m)}, 1, \mathbb{U}_2)$
- 6: Let $\mathbf{p} = \{1\{i = 1024 - r^{(e')}\}\}_i \in \mathbb{U}_N^{1024}$.
- 7: Let $\mathbf{q} = \{r^{\text{out}} - \text{adjust}(r^{(m)}, i)\}_i \in \mathbb{U}_N^{1024}$.
- 8: $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{q} \ggg r^{(e')}$
- 9: share $(r^{(m)}, r^{(e')}, r^{(w)}, r^{(t)}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q})$
- 10: $(k_0^{(\text{select})}, k_1^{(\text{select})}) \leftarrow \text{Gen}_n^{\text{select}}(r^{(w)}, r^{(t)}, 0)$
- 11: For $b \in \{0, 1\}$, $k_b = k_b^< || k_b^{\text{select}} || r_b^{(m)} || r_b^{(e')} || r_b^{(w)} || r_b^{(t)} || \mathbf{p}_b || \mathbf{q}_b$

$\text{Eval}_{n,f}^{\text{FloatToFix}}(b, k_b, (m_b, e_b))$:

- 1: Parse k_b as $k_b^< || k_b^{\text{select}} || r_b^{(m)} || r_b^{(e')} || r_b^{(w)} || r_b^{(t)} || \mathbf{p}_b || \mathbf{q}_b$
- 2: $\hat{m}_b = m_b + r_b^{(m)}$
- 3: $\hat{e}'_b = e_b + r_b^{(e')} + b \cdot (f - 23)$
- 4: $(\hat{m}, \hat{e}') = \text{reconstruct}(\hat{m}_b, \hat{e}'_b)$
- 5: $\hat{w}_b \leftarrow \text{Eval}_{24}^<(b, k_b^<, \hat{m}) + r_b^{(w)} \pmod 2$
- 6: $\hat{\mathbf{p}}'_b = \mathbf{p}_b \ggg \hat{e}'_b$
- 7: $\hat{t}_b = r_b^{(t)} + \sum_{i=0}^{1023} \text{adjust}_n(1, i + 24 \pmod{1024}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{p}}'_{b,i}$
- 8: $(\hat{w}, \hat{t}) = \text{reconstruct}(\hat{w}_b, \hat{t}_b)$
- 9: $\hat{x}_b = q_{b,\hat{e}'} + \text{Eval}_n^{\text{select}}(b, k_b^{\text{select}}, \hat{w}, \hat{t}) + \sum_{i=0}^{1023} \text{adjust}(\hat{m}, i) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{p}}'_{b,i}$
- 10: return \hat{x}_b

Figure 1: Protocol for FloatToFix.

Theorem 2. $\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{FloatToFix}}$ realizes $\text{FloatToFix}_{n,f}$ securely such that $\text{keysize}(\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{FloatToFix}}) = \text{keysize}(\text{DCF}_{24,\mathbb{U}_2}) + \text{keysize}(\Pi_n^{\text{select}}) + 2049n + 35$. In the online phase, the protocol requires 1 evaluation of $\text{DCF}_{24,\mathbb{U}_2}$ and costs communication of $2n + 70$ bits in 2 rounds.

Security proof. For $b \in \{0, 1\}$, the simulator Sim_b for FloatToFix is given (m_b, e_b) and \hat{x}_b and has to simulate the view of party b , i.e., messages $k_b^< || k_b^{\text{select}} || r_b^{(m)} || r_b^{(e')} || r_b^{(w)} || r_b^{(t)} || \mathbf{p}_b || \mathbf{q}_b$ from dealer and $\hat{m}_{1-b} || \hat{e}'_{1-b} || \hat{w}_{1-b} || \hat{t}_{1-b}$ from the other evaluator. The sim-

ulator follows the following steps:

- 1) Randomly samples $r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(m)}$ and $\hat{m}_{1-b,\text{sim}}$ from $\mathbb{U}_{2^{24}}$.
- 2) Randomly samples $r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(e)}$ and $\hat{e}'_{1-b,\text{sim}}$ from $\mathbb{U}_{2^{10}}$.
- 3) Sets $\hat{m}_{\text{sim}} = m_b + r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(m)} + \hat{m}_{1-b,\text{sim}}$ and $\hat{e}'_{\text{sim}} = e_b + r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(e)} + \hat{e}'_{1-b} + b \cdot (f - 23)$.
- 4) Randomly samples $r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(w)}$, $\hat{w}_{b,\text{sim}}$ and $\hat{w}_{1-b,\text{sim}}$ from \mathbb{U}_2 .
- 5) Generates $k_{b,\text{sim}}^{<}$ using $\text{Sim}_b^{<}$ with input \hat{m}_{sim} and output $\hat{w}_{b,\text{sim}} - r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(w)}$.
- 6) Randomly samples $p_{b,\text{sim}}$ from \mathbb{U}_N^{1024} .
- 7) Sets $p'_{b,\text{sim}} = p_{b,\text{sim}} \ggg \hat{e}'_{\text{sim}}$.
- 8) Randomly samples $r_{b,\text{sim}}^{(t)}$ and $\hat{t}_{1-b,\text{sim}}$ from \mathbb{U}_N .
- 9) Calculates $\hat{t}_{b,\text{sim}}$ using step 7 from $\text{Eval}_{n,f}^{\text{FloatToFix}}$.
- 10) Sets $\hat{w}_{\text{sim}} = \hat{w}_{b,\text{sim}} + \hat{w}_{1-b,\text{sim}}$
- 11) Sets $\hat{t}_{\text{sim}} = \hat{t}_{b,\text{sim}} + \hat{t}_{1-b,\text{sim}}$.
- 12) Generates $k_{b,\text{sim}}^{\text{select}}$ using $\text{Sim}_b^{\text{select}}$ with input $(\hat{w}_{\text{sim}}, \hat{t}_{\text{sim}})$ and output h randomly sampled from \mathbb{U}_N .
- 13) Calculates $q_{b,\text{sim},\hat{e}'_{\text{sim}}} = \hat{x}_b - h - \sum_{i=0}^{1023} \text{adjust}(\hat{m}_{\text{sim}}, i) \cdot p'_{b,\text{sim},i}$.
- 14) For $k \in [0, 1023] - \{\hat{e}'_{\text{sim}}\}$, randomly samples $q_{b,\text{sim},k}$ and sets $q_{b,\text{sim}} = \{q_{b,\text{sim},i}\}_i$.

Note. The key size of $\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{FloatToFix}}$ can be further reduced by only sending the elements in arrays p and q which needs to be accessed in the evaluation, based on the constraints on the value of e . Moreover, as the array p is set to 1 at a single index, it can be replaced with a Distributed Point Function key [2] to further reduce the key size at the cost of increased compute. We omit these optimizations here.

2. Piranha Functionalities using FSS protocols

We show how to build FSS-based protocols for functionalities used by PIRANHA [4]. These functionalities are implemented in our library to directly compare the performance of ORCA with PIRANHA on the same benchmarks.

2.1. Local-Truncation + ReLU

As discussed several prior works on secure training using local truncations, i.e., parties locally truncate their secret shares. In the FSS setting, this translates to the dealer truncating the mask and the evaluators truncating the masked value. While comparing with these works, to be apples-to-apples, we provide FSS-based protocols and optimizations for this setting. Our ideas of fusing truncations will non-activations such as ReLU or ReLU+Maxpool are also applicable for local truncations and result in lower key size compared to the naive approach of sequential computation.

A straightforward way to realize a protocol for Local-Truncation + ReLU for an n -bit input x with public scale f , with an error similar to the local truncation protocol [3], is to locally truncate x by f and use the result as an input to the protocol for ReLU from [1]. Over this protocol, we perform two optimizations:

- 1) We replace the single-round protocol for ReLU from [1] with the two-round protocol (Section 5.1 of the paper) with a smaller key size.
- 2) Since the value $x \ggg_A f$ can be represented accurately in $(n - f)$ -bits, we optimize the comparisons required for the calculation of DReLU bit to be done over a reduced bitwidth of $(n - f)$.

We present the full protocol for Local-Truncate + ReLU in Figure 2 and summarize its costs in the following theorem:

Local-Truncate + ReLU $\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{localTrReLU}}$ ($\mathbb{G}^{\text{out}} = \mathbb{U}_N$)

Gen $_{n,f}^{\text{localTrReLU}}(r^{\text{in}}, r^{\text{out}})$:

- 1: $r' = r^{\text{out}} \ggg_L f$
- 2: $(k_0^{<}, k_1^{<}) \leftarrow \text{Gen}_{n-f}^{<}(1^\lambda, r', 1, \mathbb{U}_2)$
- 3: $r^{(d)} \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{U}_2$
- 4: **share** $r^{(d)}$
- 5: $(k_0^{(\text{select})}, k_1^{(\text{select})}) \leftarrow \text{Gen}_{n-f}^{\text{select}}(r^{(d)}, r', r^{\text{out}})$
- 6: For $b \in \{0, 1\}$, $k_b = k_b^{<} || r_b^{(d)} || k_b^{(\text{select})}$

Eval $_{n,f}^{\text{localTrReLU}}(b, k_b, \hat{x})$:

- 1: Parse k_b as $k_b^{<} || r_b^{(d)} || k_b^{(\text{select})}$
- 2: $\hat{x}' = \hat{x} \ggg_L f$
- 3: $\hat{y}' = \hat{x}' + 2^{n-f-1} \pmod{2^{n-f}}$
- 4: $t_b \leftarrow \text{Eval}_{n-f}^{<}(b, k_b^{<}, \hat{y}') - \text{Eval}_{n-f}^{<}(b, k_b^{<}, \hat{x}')$
- 5: $\hat{d}_b = t_b + b \cdot 1\{\hat{y}' \geq 2^{n-f-1}\} + r_b^{(d)} \pmod{2}$
- 6: $\hat{d} = \text{reconstruct}(\hat{d}_b)$
- 7: **return** $\hat{u}_b \leftarrow \text{Eval}_{n-f}^{\text{select}}(b, k_b^{(\text{select})}, \hat{d}, \hat{x}')$

Figure 2: Protocol for Local-Truncate + ReLU. b refers to the party id.

Theorem 3. $\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{localTrReLU}}$ realizes local-truncation + ReLU securely such that $\text{keysize}(\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{localTrReLU}}) = \text{keysize}(\text{DCF}_{n-f,1}) + \text{keysize}(\Pi_{n,f}^{\text{select}}) + 1$. In the online phase, the protocol requires 2 evaluations of $\text{DCF}_{n-f,1}$ and costs communication of 2 bits in 1 round.

The naive unoptimized approach costs a key size of $\text{keysize}(\text{DCF}_{n,2n}) + 5n$ bits. For $n = 64$ and $f = 24$, our protocol costs $3 \times$ less key size. In the case when local-truncation is followed by MaxPool followed by ReLU, we follow the idea described in Appendix B (of the paper) to calculate all the internal DReLU bits on a reduced bitwidth of $n - f$.

2.2. Approximate Softmax

PIRANHA used Equation 1 (from the paper) to implement softmax with the following approximations for exponential and inverse.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{exp}(x) &= \begin{cases} \frac{x+2}{2} & \text{if } -2 < x \leq 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x \leq -2 \end{cases} \\ &= \text{relu}(x + 2)/2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\tilde{\text{inv}}(x) = \begin{cases} 2.63x^2 - 5.857x + 4.245 & \text{if } 0.5 \leq x < 1 \\ \tilde{\text{inv}}(x/2^k) \cdot 2^{-k} & \text{if } 2^{k-1} \leq x < 2^k \end{cases}$$

The expression for $\text{exp}(x)$ can be trivially realized using the protocol for local-truncation + ReLU (Section 2.1). For $\text{inv}(x)$, PIRANHA calculated k securely but revealed its value in the clear, leaking the range of x . To mimic this behaviour, we first calculate k using the protocol for multiple interval containment (Section C.1 of the paper) and reveal its value to the evaluators. Then the above polynomial can be trivially evaluated using protocols for multiplication and local-truncation.

3. Correctness of DReLU offset function

Starting with the definition of offset function, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DReLU}_n^{[r^{\text{in}}, r^{\text{out}}]}(\hat{x}) &= \text{DReLU}_n(\hat{x} - r^{\text{in}} \bmod 2^n) + r^{\text{out}} \\ &= 1\{\hat{x} - r^{\text{in}} \bmod 2^n < 2^{n-1}\} + r^{\text{out}} \end{aligned}$$

Let $\hat{y} = \hat{x} + 2^{n-1} \bmod 2^n$ and $r' = r^{\text{in}} + 2^{n-1} \bmod 2^n$. According to the above equation, the indicator function above returns 1 when \hat{x} lies in the region starting from r^{in} until r' , taking care of wraps. Now, we will simplify this expression by considering two cases.

Case 1: $r^{\text{in}} < 2^{n-1}$: This implies that $r^{\text{in}} + 2^{n-1} < 2^n$ and $r' = r^{\text{in}} + 2^{n-1}$. Hence, the expression becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DReLU}_n^{[r^{\text{in}}, r^{\text{out}}]}(\hat{x}) &= 1\{\hat{x} \in [r^{\text{in}}, r']\} + r^{\text{out}} \\ &= 1\{\hat{x} < r'\} - 1\{\hat{x} < r^{\text{in}}\} + r^{\text{out}} \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: $r^{\text{in}} \geq 2^{n-1}$: This implies that $r^{\text{in}} + 2^{n-1} \geq 2^n$ and $r' = r^{\text{in}} - 2^{n-1}$. Hence, the expression becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DReLU}_n^{[r^{\text{in}}, r^{\text{out}}]}(\hat{x}) &= 1\{\hat{x} \in [0, r'] \cup [r^{\text{in}}, 2^n - 1]\} + r^{\text{out}} \\ &= 1\{\hat{x} < r'\} + 1\{\hat{x} \geq r^{\text{in}}\} + r^{\text{out}} \\ &= 1\{\hat{x} < r'\} + 1 - 1\{\hat{x} < r^{\text{in}}\} + r^{\text{out}} \end{aligned}$$

Since the expressions in the two cases differ exactly by 1, combining the two cases, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DReLU}_n^{[r^{\text{in}}, r^{\text{out}}]}(x) &= 1\{r^{\text{in}} \geq 2^{n-1}\} + 1\{\hat{x} < r'\} \\ &\quad - 1\{\hat{x} < r^{\text{in}}\} + r^{\text{out}} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Now, to further simplify the $1\{\hat{x} < r'\}$ term, we use the following lemma from [1]:

Lemma (Lemma 1 from [1]). *Let $a, \tilde{a}, b, \tilde{b}, r \in \mathbb{U}_N$, where $a \leq b$, $\tilde{a} = a + r \bmod N$ and $\tilde{b} = b + r \bmod N$. Define 4 boolean predicates over $\mathbb{U}_N \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ as follows: $P(x)$ denotes $x < \tilde{a}$, $P'(x)$ denotes $x \leq \tilde{a}$, $Q(x)$ denotes $(x + (b - a) \bmod N) < \tilde{b}$, $Q'(x)$ denotes $(x + (b - a) \bmod N) \leq \tilde{b}$. Then, the following holds:*

$$P(x) = Q(x) + (e_a - e_x) \text{ and } P'(x) = Q'(x) + (e_a - e_x)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{where } e_a &= 1\{\tilde{a} + (b - a) > N - 1\} \text{ and} \\ e_x &= 1\{x + (b - a) > N - 1\} \end{aligned}$$

In the above lemma, if we set $a = 0, b = 2^{n-1}, b - a = 2^{n-1}, r = r^{\text{in}}, x = \hat{y}$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{a} &= a + r \bmod N = r^{\text{in}} \\ \tilde{b} &= b + r \bmod N = r^{\text{in}} + 2^{n-1} \bmod N = r' \\ P(\hat{y}) &= 1\{\hat{y} < \tilde{a}\} = 1\{\hat{y} < r^{\text{in}}\} \\ Q(\hat{y}) &= 1\{\hat{y} + 2^{n-1} \bmod N < r'\} = 1\{\hat{x} < r'\} \\ e_a &= 1\{r^{\text{in}} + 2^{n-1} > 2^n - 1\} = 1\{r^{\text{in}} \geq 2^{n-1}\} \\ e_{\hat{y}} &= 1\{\hat{y} + 2^{n-1} > 2^n - 1\} = 1\{\hat{y} \geq 2^{n-1}\} \end{aligned}$$

We observe that $Q(\hat{y})$ is the term we need. So:

$$\begin{aligned} Q(\hat{y}) &= P(\hat{y}) - e_a + e_{\hat{y}} \\ 1\{\hat{x} < r'\} &= 1\{\hat{y} < r^{\text{in}}\} - 1\{r^{\text{in}} \geq 2^{n-1}\} \\ &\quad + 1\{\hat{y} \geq 2^{n-1}\} \end{aligned}$$

Plugging this result in Equation 1, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DReLU}_n^{[r^{\text{in}}, r^{\text{out}}]}(\hat{x}) &= 1\{\hat{x} < r'\} + 1\{r^{\text{in}} \geq 2^{n-1}\} \\ &\quad - 1\{\hat{x} < r^{\text{in}}\} + r^{\text{out}} \\ &= 1\{\hat{y} < r^{\text{in}}\} - 1\{r^{\text{in}} \geq 2^{n-1}\} + 1\{\hat{y} \geq 2^{n-1}\} \\ &\quad + 1\{r^{\text{in}} \geq 2^{n-1}\} - 1\{\hat{x} < r^{\text{in}}\} + r^{\text{out}} \\ &= 1\{\hat{y} < r^{\text{in}}\} - 1\{\hat{x} < r^{\text{in}}\} + 1\{\hat{y} \geq 2^{n-1}\} + r^{\text{out}} \end{aligned}$$

4. Proof of Lemma 1

Lemma (Lemma 1 from the paper). *For a masked value $\hat{x} \in \mathbb{U}_N$ with underlying value x and random mask $r^{(x)}$ and scale f , let $\hat{y} = \text{TR}(\hat{x}, f)$ and $r^{(y)} = \text{TR}(r^{(x)}, f)$. When $\text{int}_n(x) \leq 2^{n-1} - 2^f$,*

$$x \gg_{\text{st}} f = \text{SignExt}_{n-f, n}(\hat{y} - r^{(y)})$$

Proof. To prove the above lemma, it suffices to show that when $\text{int}_n(x) \leq 2^{n-1} - 2^f$, $\hat{y} - r^{(y)} \bmod 2^{(n-f)}$ is equal to $x \gg_{\text{st}} f$ in $(n-f)$ bits as it is then sign-extended to n bits. Note that the condition $\text{int}_n(x) \leq 2^{n-1} - 2^f$ is required as when $\text{int}_n(x) > 2^{n-1} - 2^f$, the stochastic-truncation by f can produce an output of 2^{n-f-1} with a non-zero probability, which represents the smallest negative number in 2's-complement representation and is incorrect.

We begin the proof by stating the fact that when output bitwidth is $(n-f)$, the output of logical right-shift is the same as arithmetic right-shift, as the two only differ in the most significant f bits, which are removed when the output is reduced to $(n-f)$ bits. So, for a given masked input $\hat{x} \in \mathbb{U}_N$, with underlying value $x \in \mathbb{U}_N$ and random mask $r \in \mathbb{U}_N$, it suffices to prove that:

$$\text{TR}(\hat{x}, f) - \text{TR}(r, f) = \begin{cases} \text{TR}(x, f) & \text{with prob. } 1 - t \\ \text{TR}(x, f) + 1 & \text{with prob. } t \end{cases}$$

where $t = (x \bmod 2^f) \cdot 2^{-f}$. To show this, consider:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{TR}(x, f) &= \text{TR}(\hat{x} - r \bmod 2^n, f) \\
&= \text{TR}(\hat{x} - r + 2^n \cdot 1\{\hat{x} < r\}, f) \\
&= (\hat{x} - r + 2^n \cdot 1\{\hat{x} < r\}) \gg_L f \bmod 2^{(n-f)} \\
&= (\hat{x} - r) \gg_L f + 2^{n-f} \cdot 1\{\hat{x} < r\} \bmod 2^{(n-f)} \\
&= (\hat{x} - r) \gg_L f
\end{aligned}$$

Let $\hat{x}_1, r_1 \in \mathbb{U}_{2^{n-f}}$ and $\hat{x}_0, r_0 \in \mathbb{U}_{2^f}$ be numbers such that, $\hat{x} = \hat{x}_1 \cdot 2^f + \hat{x}_0$, $r = r_1 \cdot 2^f + r_0$. So, $\hat{x}_1 = \text{TR}(\hat{x}, f)$ and $r_1 = \text{TR}(r, f)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{TR}(x, f) &= (\hat{x} - r) \gg_L f \\
&= \hat{x}_1 - r_1 + (\hat{x}_0 - r_0) \gg_L f \\
&= \hat{x}_1 - r_1 + (\hat{x}_0 - r_0) \gg_A f
\end{aligned}$$

Note that the term $(\hat{x}_0 - r_0) \gg_A f$ can only take values 0 or -1 as $-2^f < \hat{x}_0 - r_0 < 2^f$. So, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{TR}(x, f) &= \hat{x}_1 - r_1 - 1\{\hat{x}_0 < r_0\} \\
\implies \hat{x}_1 - r_1 &= \text{TR}(x, f) + 1\{\hat{x}_0 < r_0\} \\
\text{TR}(\hat{x}, f) - \text{TR}(r, f) &= \text{TR}(x, f) + 1\{\hat{x}_0 < r_0\}
\end{aligned}$$

Now, to complete the proof, we only need to show that the term $1\{\hat{x}_0 < r_0\}$ takes values 0 with probability $1 - t$. We have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{x} &= x + r \bmod 2^n \\
\implies \hat{x}_0 &= (x \bmod 2^f) + r_0 \bmod 2^f
\end{aligned}$$

r_0 is a uniformly random value. Consider the case when $r_0 < 2^f - (x \bmod 2^f)$. In this case,

$$\begin{aligned}
r_0 + (x \bmod 2^f) &< 2^f \\
\implies \hat{x}_0 &= (x \bmod 2^f) + r_0 \bmod 2^f \\
&= (x \bmod 2^f) + r_0 \\
\implies \hat{x}_0 &\geq r_0 \\
\implies 1\{\hat{x}_0 < r_0\} &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

For this to happen, r_0 needs to randomly assume the value from the set $\{0, 1, \dots, 2^f - (x \bmod 2^f) - 1\}$ which happens with probability $(2^f - (x \bmod 2^f))/2^f = 1 - t$. \square

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